

Style for IRRN Contributors

Units of measure and styles vary from country to country. To improve communication and to speed the editorial process, the editors of the *International Rice Research Newsletter (IRRN)* request that contributors use the following style guidelines:

- Use the metric system in all papers. Avoid national units of measure (such as cavans, rai, etc.).

- Express all yields in tons per hectare (t/ha) or, with small-scale studies, in grams per pot (g/pot) or grams per row (g/row).

- Define in footnotes or legends any abbreviations or symbols used in a figure or table.

- Place the name or denotation of compounds or chemicals near the unit of measure. For example: 60 kg N/ha; not 60 kg/ha N.

- The US dollar is the standard monetary unit for the *IRRN*. Data in other currencies should be converted to US\$.

- Abbreviate names of standard units of measure when they follow a number. For example: 20 kg/ha.

- Express time, money, and measurement in numbers, even when the amount is less than 10. For example: 8 years; 3 kg/ha at 2-week intervals; 7%; 4 hours.

- Write out numbers below 10 except in a series containing some numbers 10 or higher and some numbers lower than 10. For example: six parts; seven tractors; four varieties. *But* There were 4 plots in India, 8 plots in Thailand, and 12 plots in Indonesia.

- Write out all numbers that start sentences. For example: Sixty insects were added to each cage; Seventy-five percent of the yield increase is attributed to fertilizer use.

- Type all contributions double-spaced. ■

Genetic evaluation and utilization

OVERALL PROGRESS

Karnataka male-sterile rice—KMS1

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A male-sterile rice plant isolated at Mandya, Karnataka, India, in 1972 was multiplied clonally at IRRI in February 1979. We designated it KMS1 (for Karnataka male-sterile). In greenhouse and field observations, female fertility appeared normal; seed-setting was 90% by hand pollination and 4–42% through natural cross-pollination. As in previous observations in India, there was no seed-set when the panicles were covered. But unlike in India, a few (1–2%) stainable pollen grains were observed under the microscope, although meiosis in those grains appeared normal. The new environment may possibly have induced this difference. As has been reported in barley, the pressure exerted by a few stainable pollen grains may not be adequate for the anthers to dehisce and shed pollen; thus, seed-setting failed when the panicles were covered.

Data gathered from 53 stubbles planted among 32 tall and 23 semidwarf

rices in the IRRI observational yield trial and hybridization block in the 1979 dry and wet seasons showed that natural cross-pollination can produce 4 to 24% seed-set. Seed-setting was higher in the dry season (17–42%) than in the wet (4–37%).

KMS1 ratoons vigorously like its male parent, C435, and is relatively free from virus attack, although it has been maintained clonally since 1972.

When KMS1 was backcrossed to its female parent IR8, the 64 progenies were fertile to varying degrees. When backcrossed to the male parent the three progenies tended to be sterile. Because the number of backcross progeny for the latter was small, we again backcrossed the male parent. The progenies (IR30638) are being grown for observation in the 1980 dry-season F₁ nursery. IR30638 was also crossed with the monogenic recessive male-sterile IR36. The F₁s (IR30431) are being planted in the 1980 dry-season nursery.

Since 1973, KMS1 has been widely used in hybridization work in Karnataka. IRRI is investigating the mechanism responsible for male sterility. ■

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Disease Resistance

Varietal reaction of rice cultivars to *Pyricularia oryzae* in Argentina

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In December 1978, 197 rice experimental lines and traditional varieties were artificially inoculated in the field. The nursery plot design, the soil fertilization, and the seeding methods were based on the techniques suggested by S.H. Ou of IRRI.

Because of a lack of natural field infection, the seedlings were sprayed at the fourth-leaf stage with a *P. oryzae* conidial suspension that had been prepared with strain cultures of the pathogen V3-78-1, V3-78-2, CU3-78, G4-78, LP5-78, and SF4-78. Such strains were isolated from infected material sent from various places in the provinces of Entre Rios, Buenos Aires (La Plata), and Santa Fe of Argentina.

The misato agar and barley seeds sterilized in misato solution were used as sporulating media. The suspension was adjusted to conidial concentration at

200,000 spores/ml, and an adhesive, Triton × 100, at a drop in 100-ml concentration, was used.

After the preliminary treatment, a wet chamber was devised to assure infection. The plot was covered with transparent polyethylene. The incubation period was 60 hours, during which dewing was superficial. At the end of this period, the seedlings continued to grow under dry, barren conditions.

Cultivar reaction was evaluated, by type of lesion, on the Standard Evaluation System for rice. Observations at: 1) the seedling (4-leaf) stage, 2) the tillering stage, 3) the flag leaf stage, and 4) the panicle stage were recorded. The responses were later compared to establish the infection evolution in the nursery.

Some cultivars kept their behavior throughout their development, but others either lost or gained resistance instead. The table summarizes the results.

Blast disease evolution caused by *P. oryzae* during the development of 197 cultivars, Argentina.

Cultivars		Blast disease ^a reaction	
no.	%	Tillering stage	Panicle stage
29	15	R	R
17	9	R	S
2	1	S	S
5	2	S	R
12	6	I	I
28	14	I	R
62	31	I	S
17	9	R	I
0	0	S	I
25	13	No records	

^aR = resistant, S = susceptible, I = intermediate.

Forty percent of the cultivars tested became susceptible during their development; only 16% gained resistance, but 22% retained their original reaction and 9% acquired an intermediate response at the end of the panicle initiation stage.

On the basis of these results, the germplasm resistant to *P. oryzae* was then selected.

The following lines are particularly recommended as parents because of their resistant response throughout the test: H114-3-3-2-1, H114-5-2-1-1, H114-5-11-

1-1, H114-23-1, H114-21-1, H115-13-1, Montiel, H115-19-1, ^a H118-1-1-1-1, H124-36-1, Lucas P.A., H118-2-1-1-1, H118-10-1, H119-3-1-1-2, ^a H119-11-1, H124-5-1-1-2, H124-5-2-2-1, ^b H124-5-3-1-1-1, H124-5-3-1-1-2, H124-6-1-1, H124-6-1-3-1-2, H124-6-1-3-2, H124-8-1-1, H124-8-1-3-1, H124-8-1-3-2, ^b H124-40-2-1, H124-40-2-2, H124-40-4-2, H127-29-1, H135-15, and H135-35.

The following cultivars, which respond to lesions from type 4 to type 6, are recommended for commercial use, mainly because of their horizontal resistance, but are not recommended as resistant progenitors: Sel. 5/CI 9703//Sesc. . . , Bluebonnet 50, H114-5-5-1-1^a, H115-20-1, H119-2-1-3, H119-2-1-4, and Inga.

This method proved useful because it allowed evaluation of 197 cultivars in the presence of a *P. oryzae* attack, identifying the inferior lines that should be eliminated. For the 1978–79 campaign, 158 lines were eliminated. ■

^aOutstanding for cultural features and commercial quality.

^bRecommended for resistance because they are highly resistant, keeping lesion type 1 from tillering to panicle stages.

Fungal fluids induce rice seedling resistance to brown spot disease

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Biological induction in plants of resistance to their pathogens is of scientific interest. At this laboratory, a high degree of protection against the brown spot pathogen was induced in 3-week-old seedlings of Dharial, Dular, and Lathisail by inoculation with spore suspension (concn 5×10^5 spores/ml) of a mildly virulent isolate 2 days before challenge inoculation. Initial studies indicated that cell-free spore germination fluid or spore extract of a mild isolate could also induce resistance, although less effectively. This prompted investigations with fungal fluids, such as

culture filtrate, replacement culture filtrate, and extracts from freshly collected and dried or freeze-dried mycelium of both isolates. The fluids were used either as foliage spray on 3-week-old seedlings 2 days before inoculation with the virulent isolate, or for seed soaking for 24 hours before sowing in pots or field plots. The plants grown in pots were artificially inoculated 3 weeks later. Those plants grown in the field were left exposed to natural infection.

Reduction in symptoms achieved with mild isolate inoculum in different treatments ranged from 62 to 79%. Preinoculation treatments with different fluids reduced symptoms by 6–52%. Fluids from the mild isolate were distinctly more effective than those from the virulent isolate. Results were best with the replacement culture filtrate, closely followed by the mycelial extract. Culture filtrate was less effective. Extracts from oven-dried or freeze-dried mycelium were significantly less effective than extracts from freshly harvested mycelium. Seed-soaking gave considerable protection for as long as 3 weeks. That induced protection was slightly less effective than foliage spray applied 2 days before inoculation, but its persistence appeared significant.

In experiments with spore germination fluids obtained from both virulent and mild isolates, spraying fluids obtained from a suspension of 10^6 spores/ml of the isolates gave substantial protection (see table). With germination fluids obtained from higher concentrations, symptom reductions increased progressively (up to 81%) for the mild isolate, but declined steadily to 18% with comparable fluids of the virulent isolate. Fungitoxicity of leaf diffusates from plants in different treatments ran almost parallel to their effects in inducing resistance. Such observations imply that some fungal metabolite present in different fluids induces resistance in rice plants to *H. oryzae* through production of fungitoxic substance in the plant tissue. When the germination fluid was exposed to different treatments, its resistance-inducing ability was often inhibited. Results indicate that the